

European Nucleotide Archive

Programmatic Read Data Submission

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EMBL-EBI

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ENA Background: What is ENA?

Open platform for the management, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data

- **Globally comprehensive scientific record** and European node of **INSDC**
- **Broad scope** covering raw data, through layers of interpretation and context
- **Connectivity** with broader EMBL-EBI resources
- Sequence data **foundation**
- Rich submission, discovery and retrieval **software, tools and services**
- **Support** through Helpdesk and training
- **Management**, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data
- **Data coordination** including project-specific data hubs and portals

Archive

Platform

Data sharing

Why is it important to share data?

- Findability
- Accessibility
- Interoperability
- Reproducibility/Reusability
- Data standards
- Community collaboration

Maximum value

Submitting data to the ENA

All data in the ENA is submitted by members of the research community

What motivates people to submit?

- Open data
- Reproducibility
- Reusability
- 3rd party access
- Archival
- **Publication**
- Downstream analyses

*The data lifecycle, from ELIXIR Europe
<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>*

Data resources at EMBL-EBI

ENA - an ELIXIR Core Data Resource

- The ENA is part of the wider ecosystem of biodata resources
- Recognised as an ELIXIR CDR and Global Core Biodata Resource by the Global Biodata Coalition
- Integration into a system of biodata resources increases value in genomics data

GLOBAL
CORE
BIODATA
RESOURCE

Data Structure at ENA

ENA Data Structure

- ENA stores huge amounts of data
 - ... from many users
 - ... with samples from many taxa
 - ... who use many different techniques
 - ... and sequence on many different platforms
- But we need to display data in a consistent manner
- A robust model is the first step in achieving this

ENA Data model

Sequence data is organised into tiers:

- **Reads:** raw sequence data
- **Assemblies:** reconstructions of actual replicons
- **Annotations:** interpretations of biological function

Annotation and **assembly** are frequently paired

ENA Metadata Model

- Data without any context has no value
- Metadata tells us how sequence data was produced
- Makes it possible to compare datasets:

*“I want to see data from Secale cereale ...
... sampled from the United Kingdom ...
... between April and June ...
... compared with the same from Germany”*

- Archives have spent a lot of time thinking about this!

The Metadata Model

CC0 Public Domain

Viruses have a range of effects on bees, but there is little information except for one bee species (*Apis mellifera*) in N. America and Europe.

Galbraith *et al.* sequenced viral metagenomes of 11 bee species in 9 countries.

Developed a pipeline to assemble contigs from the data and identify viruses.

Galbraith *et al.* 2018, article available at: <https://rdcu.be/bb3G0>

ENA Metadata Model: Study

STUDY

ENA Metadata Model: Register Study

☰ Register study (project)

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *
01-03-2027

Exploration of viral ecology in global bee communities

Viral Studies in Bees

Will you provide functional genome annotation ?

A descriptive abstract describing the project.

PubMed Citations Registration

Add PubMed Citations

PubMedId	Title	Remove
PPR8996	Investigating the viral ecology of global bee communities with high-throughput metagenomics	

Webin Submissions Portal: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

ENA Metadata Model: Register Study

ENA Webin Submissions Portal

Register study (project)

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *
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Submission Details

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Viral Studies in Bees

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PubMed Citations Registration

Add PubMed Citations +

PubMedId	Title	Remove
PPR8996	Investigating the viral ecology of global bee communities with high-throughput metagenomics	

Webin Submissions Portal: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

ENA Metadata Model: Sample

The Metadata Model

Collaborators across 4 continents sampled foraging bees

Details including the species and GPS coordinates were logged. Similar bees were homogenised to give 37 separate samples.

This information is recorded in the database.

The Metadata Model

STUDY

SAMPLE

Location: India

Host: *Apis florea*

SAMPLE

Location: Nicaragua

Host: *Apis mellifera*

SAMPLE

Location: Switzerland

Host: *Bombus impatiens*

SAMPLE

Location: Kenya

Host: *Apis mellifera*

Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

Minimum amount of information expected to describe biological samples required for registration in ENA

Sample Checklists

There is a minimum amount of information required during ENA sample registration and all samples must conform to a defined checklist of expected metadata values. The most suitable checklist for sample registration depends on the type of the sample.

These sample checklists have been developed to meet the needs of different research communities. Different communities have different requirements on the minimum metadata expected to describe biological samples. For any questions regarding checklists, contact us [here](#).

Filter by accession/name/description/field name

Accession	Name	Description
ERC000012	GSC MixS air	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000013	GSC MixS host associated	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000014	GSC MixS human associated	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000015	GSC MixS human gut	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000016	GSC MixS human oral	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000017	GSC MixS human skin	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000018	GSC MixS human vaginal	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.

The Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

You have selected **GSC MixS host associated**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	tax_id	Text field	None	Taxonomy ID of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database. Entries in the NCBI Taxonomy database have integer taxon IDs. See our tips for sample taxonomy here
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	scientific_name	Text field	None	Scientific name of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database. Scientific names typically follow the binomial nomenclature. For example, the scientific name for humans is Homo sapiens.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_alias	Text field	None	Unique name of the sample. If not selected system will auto generate an unique alias
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_title	Text field	None	Title of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_description	Text field	None	Description of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	project name	Text field	None	Name of the project within which the sequencing was organized
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	collection date	Regular expression	None	The date the sample was collected with the intention of sequencing, either as an instance (single point in time) or interval. In case no exact time is available, the date/time can be right truncated i.e. all of these are valid ISO8601 compliant times: 2008-01-23T19:23:10+00:00; 2008-01-23T19:23:10; 2008-01-23; 2008-01; 2008.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (country and/or sea)	Permitted values	None	The geographical origin of where the sample was collected from, with the intention of sequencing, as defined by the country or sea name. Country or sea names should be chosen from the INSDC country list (http://insdc.org/country.html).
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (latitude)	Regular expression	DD	The geographical origin of the sample as defined by latitude. The values should be reported in decimal

ENA Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

You have selected **GSC MixS host associated**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Add custom field

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Recommended Fields

Optional Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	trophic level	Permitted values	None	Trophic levels are the feeding position in a food chain. Microbes can be a range of producers (e.g. chemolithotroph)
<input type="checkbox"/>	observed biotic relationship	Permitted values	None	Description of relationship(s) between the subject organism and other organism(s) it is associated with. E.g., parasite on species X; mutualist with species Y. The target organism is the subject of the relationship, and the other organism(s) is the object.
<input type="checkbox"/>	known pathogenicity	Text field	None	To what is the entity pathogenic, for instance plant, fungi, bacteria
<input type="checkbox"/>	relationship to oxygen	Permitted values	None	Is this organism an aerobe, anaerobe? Please note that aerobic and anaerobic are valid descriptors for microbial environments
<input type="checkbox"/>	propagation	Text field	None	The type of reproduction from the parent stock. Values for this field is specific to different taxa. For phage or virus: lytic/lysogenic/temperate/obligately lytic. For plasmids: incompatibility group. For eukaryotes: sexual/asexual. Mandatory for MIGs of eukaryotes, plasmids and viruses.
<input type="checkbox"/>	observed host symbionts		None	The taxonomic name of the organism(s) found living in mutualistic, commensalistic, or parasitic symbiosis with the specific host.
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample collection device	Text field	None	The device used to collect an environmental sample. It is recommended to use terms listed under environmental sampling device (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO) and/or terms listed under specimen collection device (http://

The Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

- Recommended and optional fields are encouraged to provide maximum metadata for samples
- Custom Fields bar enables users to add custom sample attributes
- More metadata = more easily searchable and reusable data

Download spreadsheet to register samples

Please select the most appropriate checklist group, checklist and checklist fields. Download an empty spreadsheet template, fill in the spreadsheet and submit the spreadsheet using WebID.

Select checklist group | Select checklist | **Select checklist fields** | Download spreadsheet template

You have selected **ENA Native Metagenome Checklist**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Add custom field Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Recommended Fields

Optional Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample collection device or method	Text field	None	The method or device employed for collecting the sample
<input type="checkbox"/>	location and growth condition	Text field	None	Publication reference in the form of PubMed ID (pmid), digital object identifier (doi) or url for location and growth condition specifications of the organism/culture. Mandatory for WGS and RNA-Seq. Specimens
<input type="checkbox"/>	amount or size of sample collected	Integer expression	Liquid/LCM	Amount or size of sample (volume, mass or array) that was collected
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample storage duration	Integer expression	Hours/Days/Weeks/Months/Years	Duration for which sample was stored
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample storage temperature	Integer expression	°C	Temperature at which sample was stored. (e.g. -80)
<input type="checkbox"/>	growth condition	Text field	None	A text field to record any specific growth media/particular conditions used to grow organisms or parts of the organism. This includes isolated environments such as cultures and open environments such as field studies
<input type="checkbox"/>	temperature	Integer expression	°C	Temperature of water at the time of taking the sample. Format: an integer, ENA-PID 775 (EMBL) or optional: for °C. Example: 17.102

Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

- ENA metadata checklists guided by standards working groups and the communities
 - Keep up with requirements within communities
- Rich standardised metadata facilitates linking to source information
- General minimum requirements (INSDC)
 - Organism information mandatory and linked with NCBI taxonomy
 - INSDC spatiotemporal policy: mandatory provision of collection date & geographic location
 - INSDC missing value reporting

INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update (03-03-2023)

[Home](#) > [News & Announcements](#) > [INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update \(03-03-2023\)](#)

INSDC continues its aim to increase the number of sequences for which the origin of the sample can be precisely located in time and space through harmonisation of accurate geographical annotation and date and time of collection information.

The Metadata Model: Taxonomy

Taxon: 256318
metagenome [species]

Lineage
unclassified sequences, metagenomes

Tax Tree

Abbreviated lineage

- > unclassified sequences
- ▼ metagenomes
- ▼ ecological metagenomes
 - activated carbon metagenome [species]
 - activated sludge metagenome [species]
 - aerosol metagenome [species]
 - air metagenome [species]
 - alkali sediment metagenome [species]
 - anaerobic digester metagenome [species]
 - archaean metagenome [species]
 - ant fungus garden metagenome [species]
 - aquaculture metagenome [species]
 - aquatic metagenome [species]
 - aquifer metagenome [species]
 - ballast water metagenome [species]
 - beach sand metagenome [species]

Taxon: 256318
metagenome [species]

Lineage
unclassified sequences, metagenomes

Tax Tree

Abbreviated lineage

- > unclassified sequences
- ▼ metagenomes
- > ecological metagenomes
 - metagenome [species]
 - ▼ organismal metagenomes
 - algae metagenome [species]
 - amphibian metagenome [species]
 - annelid metagenome [species]
 - ant metagenome [species]
 - aquatic viral metagenome [species]
 - bat metagenome [species]
 - beetle metagenome [species]
 - bird metagenome [species]
 - blood metagenome [species]
 - bovine gut metagenome [species]
 - bovine metagenome [species]

View: XML
Download: XML
Navigation: Show
Tax Tree: Hide
Related ENA Records: Show

- The taxon ID is an essential attribute of your ENA samples

- Make sure you use environmental taxonomy for metagenome samples

insect metagenome

Taxonomy ID: 1234904

Scientific name: **insect metagenome**

Inherited blast name: **metagenomes**

Rank: **species**

Apis mellifera

Taxonomy ID: 7460

Apis mellifera Linnaeus, 1758

Inherited blast name: **bees**

Rank: **species**

ENA Metadata Model: Experiment

The Metadata Model: Experiments

Viruses were isolated and their DNA/RNA extracted.

Following random, unbiased amplification, the material was sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq in 37 separate single-end experiments.

The Metadata Model

ENA Metadata Model: Sample

The Metadata Model: Runs

```
@SRR6033657.1 1/1
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACCTCATCCGGTAGAGCGAATGATTATATCCCTTGTTTTCTAAACTACCTCAACCTATTCTC
TACCTCCAAC TAGTTGAGTACCTGTCTTTCTTTCTTTATGAATCCTTTGTGTTTCGGTTCATATTGCCCC
+
--AB8CEF, ,C: :CFEFGFGGFDGGG>+CC,,<@++8,,<C,,,,,<;CC,,,,6<,,,,,;:9:C,,
9:C,:CC@C,,,9C@,,,9,,,99?,959?@E,,,::,55,,,,,99AA+++44,,,9,44,+
@SRR6033657.2 2/1
TTTGATGATGATTCCTTTCTCTTTTCATTGATGATCCCATCTGATTCTAATCCATTATTCATTCAATCCCATTTTATGA
AAATTCATTCCGATTCCTTTCAATGTGGTTGTCGCTAGTTGGTCAGGTTTTGGTGGAGTTCGCTAGATGGT
+
ACC@<E, ,C<9EGFGGGGGGGGGGGGGGGG99EFFFFEFG9,CCEC, ,<CE,CC,CEEC,CCE, ,<C@C,CCE, ,<,
, ,<CEE,CCE, ,<AE@FBEE, ,<:, ,8C,47,+:, ,8A,,,9,9D,+9,,,99,4?,+,9,,9
@SRR6033657.3 3/1
CACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACCTCTCTCGGTTTGGTTTCATCCACATCCCCAGTTCCTTACCTATATTGCCCTCTTTC
CTCTCTTCCAACCTCTCTTTCTTCATCATCCATCCCTCCACACATCTCACCCCTTTCTTTTTATT
+
--8A,CEEA@E:@CFGFGGGGGGGGFCFFFE, ,CCEDEFCC8C, ,;:, ,<6C,CC, ,;:, ,<9,::, ,8C@,
, ,99CC, ,6,<, ,<:6:,9,95:@,::,59,::,:::4, ,5,9?,9AE+495, ,449+,
@SRR6033657.4 4/1
GTTTGTCCCTCAAACCTCCC AAAAAGCTAGGGAAGCTAGCTAGGCACACCTCTTGCCATCTTACTACACCCACTTTCA
CTTATCCATTCCATTCCTCCCTCCACTCACTTTTCTCATCAATCACTTTTTTATGTGCGTTTATGTTTCATATC
+
-ACB<FCCCF8E-CDFGFGGGGGGCGGDF8, ,CF9, ,;:, ,;:, ,<, ,<, ,<, ,:
8,8, :99, ,<9,66<,996, ,6<@6@, ,5:, ,959,9,9, ,9, ,5,+, ,99,+4+,4,99, ,94
@SRR6033657.5 5/1
ACCATCTGAGGGAACCTTTGGCGCCTCCGTTACCTTTTAGGAGGCTACCGCCCAGTCAAACCTCCCGTCAGACACTG
TCTCCGATAGCCATCACCTATCTGGGTTACAGTGGCCATAACACAAGGGTAGTATCCCATCCTCCTCCT
+
@CC9CEFGF, -,B@CFGFGGAFGGGGGGGGGGGGEGGEC, ,6, ,;6+:67@, :9, ,;:, ,<C@C@, ,:
6CC, <C6?C++8+, ,;:5BA=?,A5, ,4:7, ,;:, ,49,AB,A,A,+, ,+9,+E,?A<A, ,8,74,?=4?:,
```

The result of these experiments was a collection of 37 separate FASTQ files.

These were compressed and uploaded to a database, where they underwent processing and waited to be made public.

The Metadata Model: Runs

ENA Metadata Model: Read Spreadsheet

You have selected **Fastq File Type**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Show Description

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Field Label	Permitted Value
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample	Sample	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	study	Study	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	instrument_model	Instrument model	Permitted values
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_name	Library name	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_source	Library source	Permitted values
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_selection	Library selection	Permitted values
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_strategy	Library strategy	Permitted values
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_layout	Library layout	Permitted values
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	file_name	File name	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	file_md5	File checksum	

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

The Metadata Model: Analysis

```
>ENA|PEHZ01000001|PEHZ01000001.1 Insect metagenome contig_0_374_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GATACGTGTGCAGGTGCAAGGGTATGTGCATGGAGGGGTGCGTGTATAGGTGCGAGGATG
TGTGGGGTGTGTAGGTGGAAGTGTGTGTGCATGGAGGATACGTGTGCAGGTGCAAGGGTA
TGTGCATGGAGGGTGCCTGTATAGTCCGAGGATGTGTGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTGAGGGT
GTGTGTAGGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTGAGTGTGTATGTGCATGGAGGGGTGTCAGGTGCAA
GGGTATGTGCATGGAGGGTGCCTGTATAGTCCGAGGATGTGTGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTG
AGGGTGTGTGTAGGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTGAGTGTGTATGTGCATGGAGGGGTGTCAGG
TGCAAGGGTATGTG
>ENA|PEHZ01000002|PEHZ01000002.1 Insect metagenome contig_2_497_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACATACTAGGGTTAAAATACCCTAAAGTAGAAGCAAAAGTTA
ATATATTAACGCATAACTATGAGATACTATTTCTCTGTATGAAAATGATTAAGGATTAG
TATGAGAATCTACGGGTTTTCTATTTTCATCTGAGTTTATGTCTGAGTTCTATTATATCTA
TTTAAACGAGAATAAAGAAACCTTAGATACTTTTATAACACAAGAGATATTAACAATTT
CTATTCACGTTTTATTTAGTAGGTATGAATTAAGAACTATCTAAGATTCAATTAATTCGAT
AATGAAAGAAAATGAATGGTTAGAAAAAGAAAATAAAAACTTTCATTTACTTCTAGAATC
TGGTAGTAACCTAATAGAGATGATAATTTGATTCATGCAAGATTATAGCGGAGTT
AAAAATAGTGAGTAAAAATTGACCAAGTTTCAGTGGAGGTCGCTAGATGGTCCGGGTAGGTG
GAGGTCGCTAGATGGTC
>ENA|PEHZ01000003|PEHZ01000003.1 Insect metagenome contig_4_469_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACATCATTGCGCTAAATGCAAGTTCTGGATGCTTTTGGACTT
TTCCATGAAGTGATGTTTCTCCATCATCGACAGTCAATGTTGTACGCGAATCAGGAATC
GTAGTCGATTGACTCACCGAGTCATCATCGGGCTCGACTGCGATGAACATAATCGTG
TCTGATGCATGAAAGGTACTGGGCCAATTTGTGCGACCGAATTTGAAAAGTACGCCGTACC
TCAGGAATCATCGGTGTGGGAACTTTGTAAAAACATCAGTGTCTATTTATCAAGACGCT
TTGAAAAGGGCGCATCCGGCCACAGGGTCTTTAAGCTCAGTATTTGCCACAGTATCAGAA
AACCGGCAACTATAAACAGACCCGTGCTGCGTTTGAATAATCCTTCCAACAAGGCCCTT
CTTCGTCATTTGATCGAAATGGGGCCTGGTGGAGGTCGCTAGATGGTC
>ENA|PEHZ01000004|PEHZ01000004.1 Insect metagenome contig_8_628_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACTCAAACCTCCAAAGGTGATTCGTAGCTTAAAATAACCCAC
TATCGCTATCGTAATGAATTTCTATCTTGAATCTCACTACCTGGTTTTTCAGCGGCTTTAAJ
```

Read data for one of the samples was put through an assembly program (SPAdes) to produce a set of contigs which could be searched for evidence of viral origins.

The Metadata Model: Analysis

The Metadata Model: Submit assembly

```
STUDY      TODO
SAMPLE     TODO
RUN_REF    TODO
ASSEMBLYNAME  TODO
ASSEMBLY_TYPE  primary metagenome
COVERAGE   TODO
PROGRAM    TODO
PLATFORM   TODO
MINGAPLENGTH  TODO
MOLECULETYPE  genomic DNA
FASTA      primary_metagenome.fasta.gz
```

The Metadata Model

ENA Metadata Model

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Project description and metadata

Project: [PRJNA407112](#)

The ecology of bee viruses is complex, as viruses are readily shared among bee species and plants. However, our understanding of bee viral communities is primarily derived from studies of North America and European *Apis mellifera* honey bee populations. Here, we develop a novel pipeline to rapidly, inexpensively, and robustly screen for bee viruses. This pipeline includes purification of encapsulated RNA/DNA viruses, sequence-independent amplification, high throughput sequencing, integrated assembly of contigs, and screening through a series of filters to identify contigs specifically corresponding to viral sequences. We evaluated samples of honey bees and co-foraging non-*Apis* bee species (12 bee species in total) from 9 countries and 5 continents. We identified sequences corresponding to (-)ssRNA, (-)ssRNA, dsRNA, and ssDNA viruses. Overall, 127 contigs corresponding to novel viruses (previously not observed in bees), with 29 represented by >0.1% of the reads in a given sample. These 29 contigs corresponded to 9 viral families, including 6 viral families that have not been previously observed in bees. These viruses and viral families were distributed across multiple regions and species. This study provides a robust pipeline for analysis of insect viruses, and greatly expands our understanding of the diversity of viruses found in bee communities.

Show More

Organism: [insect metagenome](#)

Secondary Study Accession: SRP117625

Study Title: Investigating the viral ecology of global bee communities with high-throughput metagenomics

Center Name: Columbia

Study Name: insect metagenome

ENA-REFSEQ: N

PROJECT-ID: 407112

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2017-09-15

ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2023-05-19

Read Files

Show Column Selection

Download report: [JSON](#) [TSV](#) [Get download script](#) [Download selected files](#)

Study Accession	Sample Accession	Tax Id	Scientific Name	Generated FASTQ files: FTP	SRA files: FTP
PRJNA407112	SAMN07634932	1234904	insect metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033667.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033667
PRJNA407112	SAMN07634933	1234904	insect metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033668.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033668
PRJNA407112	SAMN07634924	1234904	insect metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033675.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033675
PRJNA407112	SAMN07634949	1234904	insect metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033691.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033691
PRJNA407112	SAMN07634953	1234904	insect metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033662.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033662

Run-centric data table

General

View: XML
XML (STUDY)

Download: XML
XML (STUDY)

Cross References: Show

ORCID Data Claims: Show

Related ENA Records: Show

Navigate around the object

Data

Read Files: Hide

Wgs Files: Show

Navigate on data

Tags

xref

EuropePMC

Information for a single run

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>

ENA Metadata Model: Navigation Bar

- View project metadata
- Show/hide different information about project
- Explore cross-references related to project
- Explore reads/analyses files

General

View:	XML
	XML (STUDY)
Download:	XML
	XML (STUDY)
Cross References:	Show
Publications:	Show
ORCID Data Claims:	Show
Related ENA Records:	Show

Data

Read Files:	Hide
Wgs Files:	Show

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Organism: [insect metagenome](#)
Secondary Study Accession: SRP117625
Study Title: Investigating the viral ecology of global bee communities with high-throughput metagenomics
Center Name: Columbia
Study Name: insect metagenome
ENA-REFSEQ: N
PROJECT-ID: 407112
ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2017-09-15
ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2023-05-19

Related ENA Records

Result	Count
Experiment	37
Assembly	1
Genome assembly contig set	1
Run	37

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Experiment: SRX3183290

Illumina MiSeq sequencing; Kenya (Naivasha)

Organism: [insect metagenome](#)
Experiment Accession: SRX3183290
Instrument Platform: ILLUMINA
Instrument Model: Illumina MiSeq
Center Name: SUB3040496
Library Layout: SINGLE
Library Strategy: WGS
Library Source: METAGENOMIC
Library Name: KNN3
Library Selection: RANDOM PCR

Show More

Read Files

Show Column Selection

Download report: [JSON](#) [TSV](#)

Get download script

Download selected files

Download All

Study Accession	Sample Accession	Experiment Accession	Run Accession	Tax Id	Scientific Name	Generated FASTQ files:	Sub
PRJNA407112	SAMN07634953	SRX3183290	SRR6033662	1234904	insect metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033662.fastq.gz	

General

View: [XML](#)

Download: [XML](#)

Cross References: [Show](#)

ORCID Data Claims: [Show](#)

Data

Read Files: [Hide](#)

Tags

environment by geolocation

terrestrial

freshwater

New tags feature

Annotations of ENA objects

Controlled textual annotations provided to metadata objects to facilitate search and filtering

ENA Metadata Model: other features

Navigation & Cross References

- Taxon:
[Taxon:1234904](#)
- EuropePMC:
[PMC5995813](#)
- MGnify:
[MGYS00005464](#)
- WGS:
[PEHZ01000000](#)

Organism:	insect metagenome
Secondary Study Accession:	SRP117625
Study Title:	Investigating the viral ecology of global bee communities with high-throughput metagenomics
Center Name:	Columbia
Study Name:	insect metagenome
ENA-REFSEQ:	N
PROJECT-ID:	407112
ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC:	2017-09-15
ENA-LAST-UPDATE:	2023-05-19

Publications

Publications citing this record

Investigating the viral ecology of global bee communities with high-throughput metagenomics.

Galbraith DA, Fuller ZL, Ray AM, Brockmann A, Frazier M, Gikungu MW, Martinez JFI, Kapheim KM, Kerby JT, Kocher SD, Losyev O, Muli E, Patch HM, Rosa C, Sakamoto JM, Stanley S, Vaudo AD, Grozinger CM.

Department of Entomology, Center for Pollinator Research, Huck Institutes of the Life Sciences Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA, USA. dag5031@gmail.com.

Sci Rep 8(1): 8879 (2018 Jun)

[Show abstract](#)

[Unpaywall \(pdf\)](#)

[DOI \(doi\)](#)

[Europe_PMC \(html\)](#)

[Europe_PMC \(pdf\)](#)

ENA Metadata Model: other features

Cross-reference Search

The ENA Xref service holds cross-references to a number of external data resources linked to ENA records. These cross-reference sources include both services operated by colleagues at EMBL-EBI (such as UniProt and Ensembl) as well as those operated outside EMBL-EBI (including SILVA and RFAM).

The update and frequency of each source is dependent on their own release cycle and/or internal processes, with ENA supporting updates as frequently as once a week.

These cross-references can also be explored programmatically using the Xref API.

If you would be interested in registering your resource as part of our cross-reference service, you can request to be added as a new Xref source here and a member of the team will get into contact with you to discuss your eligibility.

Search by Source Search by ENA record Source Details

Xref Source: Accession: Target: Expanded: Search

EMBL-EBI | MGnify

MGnify

Submit, analyse, discover and compare microbiome data

Overview Submit data Text search Sequence search Browse data About Help

Home > Studies > MGYS00005464

Study MGYS00005464

Investigating the viral ecology of global bee communities with high-throughput metagenomics

Overview Analysis summary

Last updated: Fri May 22 2020

Map Satellite

External links

- of ENA website (SRP117625)

Organism: [insect metagenome](#)

Secondary Study Accession: [SRP117625](#)

Study Title: Investigating the viral ecology of global bee communities with high-throughput metagenomics

Center Name: Columbia

Study Name: insect metagenome

ENA-REFSEQ: N

PROJECT-ID: 407112

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2017-09-15

ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2023-05-19

Navigation & Cross References

- Taxon: Taxon:1234904
- EuropePMC: PMC5995813
- MGnify: MGYS00005464
- WGS: PEHZ01000000

Data Submission at ENA

Data Submission at ENA

- There are three submissions routes
- *'Interactive Submission'*:
 - Use your browser to fill out web forms describing your work
- *'Programmatic Submission'*:
 - Describe your work in XML/JSON documents, submit them using cURL
- *'Webin-CLI'*:
 - Smart submission interface, makes use of command line

Data Submission: Interactive

- Register your objects using your browser
- Familiar and largely accessible
- Prepare spreadsheets for bigger submissions

ENA Webin Submissions Portal

Support | Manage Account | Logout

Register study (project)

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.]*
22-05-2024

Study Name
Arabidopsis mutation accumulation

Will you provide functional genome annotation?

Short descriptive study title*
Testing de novo mutation calling artefacts by re-sequencing single mutation accumulation

Detailed study abstract*
To test for the possibility that mutation bias results could in part be artifacts of a pooled-seedling sequencing approach, we re-sequenced entire rosettes of siblings (individual plants) of one mutation accumulation line and asked if the distribution of variation called (i.e., putative somatic mutations around transcription start and termination sites) was similar to the patterns seen with the seedling pools of the 107 individual lines described in the preceding section. Specifically, we grew 10 siblings and extracted DNA from 3-week old whole rosettes. Barcoded PCR-free libraries for

PubMed Citations Registration

Add PubMed Citations +

PubMedId	Title	Remove
9784120	Arabidopsis thaliana: a model plant for genome analysis.	

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Checklist	ERC000013	GSC MIXS host associated							
2	tax_id	scientific_name	sample_alias	sample_title	sample_description	sample_derived_from	collection_date	geographic_location (country and/or sea)	geographic_location (latitude)	geographic_location (longitude)
3	#units								DD	DD
4										
5										

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	FileType	fastq	Read submission file type									
2	sample	study	instrument_model	library_name	library_source	library_selection	library_strategy	library_layout	forward_file_name	forward_file_md5	reverse_file_name	reverse_file_md5
3												
4												

Data Submission: Programmatic

- Prepare an XML/JSON file describing your submission
- Send this to us via HTTPS
- Correct format for JSON/XML files important for successful submission and validation of data.

- Example cURL command:

```
curl -u username:password \  
-F "SAMPLE=@sample.xml" \  
-F "SUBMISSION=@submission.xml" \  
"https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/drop-box/submit/"
```

```
<SUBMISSION>  
  <ACTIONS>  
    <ACTION>  
      <ADD/>  
    </ACTION>  
  </ACTIONS>  
</SUBMISSION>
```

```
<SAMPLE_SET>  
<SAMPLE alias="MF5176V2" center_name="">  
<TITLE>human gastric microbiota, mucosal</TITLE>  
<SAMPLE_NAME>  
<TAXON_ID>1284369</TAXON_ID>  
<SCIENTIFIC_NAME>stomach metagenome</SCIENTIFIC_NAME>  
<COMMON_NAME></COMMON_NAME>  
</SAMPLE_NAME>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<TAG>collection date</TAG>  
<VALUE>2010</VALUE>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<TAG>host body site</TAG>  
<VALUE>Mucosa of stomach</VALUE>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<TAG>human-associated environmental package</TAG>  
<VALUE>human-associated</VALUE>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<TAG>geographic location (latitude)</TAG>  
<VALUE>1.81</VALUE>  
<UNITS>DD</UNITS>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<TAG>geographic location (longitude)</TAG>  
<VALUE>-78.76</VALUE>  
<UNITS>DD</UNITS>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<TAG>geographic location (country and/or sea)</TAG>  
<VALUE>Colombia</VALUE>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<TAG>geographic location (region and locality)</TAG>  
<VALUE>Tumaco</VALUE>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<TAG>environment (biome)</TAG>  
<VALUE>oast</VALUE>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<TAG>project name</TAG>  
<VALUE>test12V2</VALUE>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<TAG>environment (feature)</TAG>  
<VALUE>human-associated habitat</VALUE>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<TAG>environmental medium</TAG>  
<VALUE>gastric fluid</VALUE>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<TAG>broad-scale environmental context</TAG>  
<VALUE>human gut</VALUE>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<TAG>environmental medium</TAG>  
<VALUE>gastric fluid</VALUE>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<TAG>local environmental context</TAG>  
<VALUE>human gut</VALUE>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
<TAG>ENA-CHECKLIST</TAG>  
<VALUE>ERC00015</VALUE>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
</SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>  
</SAMPLE>  
</SAMPLE_SET>
```

Data Submission: Webin-CLI

- Submit your data in a single step
- Pre-submission validation
- Confidence that your submission has worked
- Describe your submission in a manifest file:

```
NAME reads_01
PLATFORM Illumina
INSTRUMENT NextSeq 500
INSERT_SIZE 200
LIBRARY_NAME library_01
LIBRARY_STRATEGY RNA-Seq
LIBRARY_SOURCE Transcriptomic
LIBRARY_SELECTION RT-PCR
SAMPLE ERS3194300
STUDY ERP108573
FASTQ reads_01.fastq.gz
```

```
@SRR2960126.1 1/1
GCCAGCTATACGTTCTTTGTGATGGGGCTTTATGTAAGGGATGGGTGGAAGCTGACCCCTGGCTAGAACGAAAAGACTGCTAT
TGTGAAGTTA
+
=:7AD=D?FDB??ACQHGGEHCEHC@GDG>GDGHFF@9?C<38BFEAChID>EEC>A3@;?=:ABCA?
@@@B-&B-&B->ACCACCCAD3@#@
@SRR2960126.2 2/1
GTGGGTAACATTTGGAACAGAAAAACAAAAGTAGAATGGTGGTGAGGAGAACAATAAAATGACTATCATTAAATTATCATTGTA
GATGTATATC
+
CCFFDFHHHHHIIJIIJJJJJJJJIIII?
DGIJJJBFHIFGGGIJIIJJJJHHHHFFFFFDEEEEDFEDEEEDEEEDDDDDDEEFFDD
@SRR2960126.3 3/1
CTTTTAAACAAGATTTTTTAAAAAATGCTGTGCTAATCACTAGCAAAAACCTAATTTGCTAGTTGCATTGGAAAGATATGACT
TGACAATTTA
+
CCFFDFHDDFFGHHHIIIIJJJJJJIGHIIJJJJJJJJJJJJJJGJIGHHHHHFFFFFDECCDDDEEEDDD
DDDDDDDDDD
@SRR2960126.4 4/1
GCTTTTTTTCGCAACGATGGAATCGATCAATTTGTTATTGTGACAGCTAAATTGATAAAACAAAATGATACAGTTTCAAATGATCAAAA
ATTTGACAGA
+
@-?DDDBDFBHD<FBHAHBD@FGIEDHGH?7BB9BFGHIDF@===FCGEGGH3AEHC;@@DDF<C>;A&AC:
5-5;>@C@CC::@ACCB@C:4>:(2
```

- Only way to submit assembly and annotated data

ENA - Submission Tools & Data Portals

Programmatic Data Submission

Programmatic Data Submission: Webin Portal

Welcome to the Webin Submissions Portal

You can use this service for a range of submission activities as well as reports on your submissions. For help with submitting your data, including the use of this interface, please refer to our Help Guides. Please familiarise yourself with the different options available. New users are advised to take a moment to understand the interface.

•Studies tab

- Used for registering studies and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered studies

•Samples tab

- Used to register new samples, requesting taxonomy for novel/unidentified/published species and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered samples

•Raw reads/experiments tab

- Used to register runs/experiments and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered runs/experiments
- Can also be used to track run files validation/processing

•ENA Metadata Model showing data objects and data structure

Studies (Projects)

Studies Report

- + Register Samples
- + Register Novel Taxonomy
- + Submit XMLs (advanced)

Samples

Samples Report

Raw Reads (Experiments and Runs)

- + Runs Report
- + Run Files Report
- + Run Processing Report
- + Unsubmitted Files Report

Data Analyses

Assemblies and annotated sequences must be submitted with **Webin-CLI**. Other analyses can be submitted as XMLs.

- + Generate Annotated Sequence Spreadsheet
- + Submit XMLs (advanced)
- + Analyses Report
- + Analysis File Report
- + Analysis Processing Report

•Analyses tab

- Used to download annotated sequences template spreadsheet and view submitted analyses metadata.
- Can also be used to track analyses files processing.

Programmatic Data Submission: Webin Account

- Each submission requires a Webin account.
- Can be created by submitting web form on the Webin Portal page.
- Requires fields such as centre name, country and user credentials.
- Fields such as centre name, contact information can be updated.
- Metagenomics consent box to allow MGnify to access and analyse metagenomic data.

Account Details

Abbreviated center name	Password
Full center name	Confirm Password
Laboratory Name	
Address	
Country	

Contact Information

Add At Least One Contact

No Sensitive Data

I confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable.

Metagenomics Consent

By keeping this box checked you give consent to the EBI MGnify team to analyse those data for which you have requested a pre-publication confidential hold. Note that the data as well as the analysis results will remain confidential until the specified release date of the associated sequencing study. If you are also requesting assembly of your data by MGnify, you also give consent to MGnify to submit these assemblies to your ENA study on your behalf. MGnify will not change any metadata or data you have already submitted but may need to perform updates to submissions performed by their team in exceptional circumstances. This service provides pre-publication state-of-the-art analysis results, along with visualisations, that you may use in subsequent publications. The service is described in <http://europepmc.org/article/MED/31696235> and we kindly request, should you use these analyses in your publications, that you cite this paper.

I give consent and confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable

Save Cancel

Programmatic Data Submission: Study

- Study required for each submission at the ENA.
- Groups data objects under one project.
- Authority on release date of data objects linked to a study. This can be included in the submission XML/JSON.
- Add publications and study attributes to study metadata.

```
"projects": [  
  {  
    "alias": "uniqueAliasrequired",  
    "name": "Human Gut Microbiota Study",  
    "title": "Exploration of the diversity human gastric microbiota",  
    "description": "The genome sequences of gut microbes were obtained using...",  
    "sequencingProject": {},  
    "attributes": [  
      {  
        "tag": "study keyword",  
        "value": "human study"  
      }  
    ],  
    "project_links": [  
      {  
        "xrefLink": {  
          "db": "PUBMED",  
          "id": "25035323"  
        }  
      }  
    ]  
  }  
]
```

```
<PROJECT_SET>  
  <PROJECT alias="cheddar_cheese">  
    <NAME>WGS Streptomyces iranensis</NAME>  
    <TITLE>Characterisation of Microbial Diversity and...</TITLE>  
    <DESCRIPTION>This study aimed to characterise the interaction of microbial...</DESCRIPTION>  
    <SUBMISSION_PROJECT>  
      <SEQUENCING_PROJECT/>  
    </SUBMISSION_PROJECT>  
  </PROJECT>  
</PROJECT_SET>
```

Programmatic Data Submission: Sample

- Sample metadata registered using XML or JSON file format.
- Range of sample checklists to choose from including Environmental, Pathogen, Plant and Marine checklists.
- Checklists include required, recommended and mandatory metadata fields.
- Mandatory minimum metadata fields for all checklists include taxonomy information, sample details, collection dates and geographic location.

```
"samples": {
  {
    "alias": "uniqueAlias",
    "title": "human gut microbiota, mucosal",
    "organism": {
      "taxonId": "408170"
    },
    "attributes": [
      {
        "tag": "project name",
        "value": "human gut study"
      },
      {
        "tag": "collection date",
        "value": "2010-01-20"
      },
      {
        "tag": "host body site",
        "value": "Mucosa of stomach"
      },
      {
        "tag": "human-associated environmental package",
        "value": "human-associated"
      },
      {
        "tag": "geographic location (latitude)",
        "value": "1.81",
        "unit": "DD"
      },
      {
        "tag": "geographic location (longitude)",
        "value": "-78.76",
        "unit": "DD"
      },
      {
        "tag": "geographic location (country and/or sea)",
        "value": "Colombia"
      },
      {
        "tag": "geographic location (region and locality)",
        "value": "Tumaco"
      },
      {
        "tag": "environment (biome)",
        "value": "coast"
      },
      {
        "tag": "environment (feature)",
        "value": "human-associated habitat"
      },
      {
        "tag": "environmental medium",
        "value": "gastric fluid"
      },
      {
        "tag": "broad-scale environmental context",
        "value": "human gut"
      },
      {
        "tag": "local environmental context",
        "value": "human gut"
      },
      {
        "tag": "ena-checklist",
        "value": "ERC000015"
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

```
<SAMPLE_SET>
  <SAMPLE alias="MY5176V2" center_name="">
    <TITLE>human gastric microbiota, mucosal</TITLE>
    <SAMPLE_NAME>
      <TAXON_ID>1284369</TAXON_ID>
      <SCIENTIFIC_NAME>stomach metagenome</SCIENTIFIC_NAME>
      <COMMON_NAME></COMMON_NAME>
    </SAMPLE_NAME>
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>
      <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>collection date</TAG>
        <VALUE>2010</VALUE>
      </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
      <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>host body site</TAG>
        <VALUE>Mucosa of stomach</VALUE>
      </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
      <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>human-associated environmental package</TAG>
        <VALUE>human-associated</VALUE>
      </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
      <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>geographic location (latitude)</TAG>
        <VALUE>1.81</VALUE>
        <UNITS>DD</UNITS>
      </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
      <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>geographic location (longitude)</TAG>
        <VALUE>-78.76</VALUE>
        <UNITS>DD</UNITS>
      </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
      <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>geographic location (country and/or sea)</TAG>
        <VALUE>Colombia</VALUE>
      </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
      <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>geographic location (region and locality)</TAG>
        <VALUE>Tumaco</VALUE>
      </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
      <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>environment (biome)</TAG>
        <VALUE>coast</VALUE>
      </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
      <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>project name</TAG>
        <VALUE>test12V2</VALUE>
      </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
      <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>environment (feature)</TAG>
        <VALUE>human-associated habitat</VALUE>
      </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
      <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>environmental medium</TAG>
        <VALUE>gastric fluid</VALUE>
      </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
      <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>broad-scale environmental context</TAG>
        <VALUE>human gut</VALUE>
      </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
      <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>local environmental context</TAG>
        <VALUE>human gut</VALUE>
      </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>
      <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>
        <TAG>ENA-CHECKLIST</TAG>
        <VALUE>ERC000015</VALUE>
      </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>
  </SAMPLE>
</SAMPLE_SET>
```

Programmatic Data Submission: Upload files

- Raw read sequence files need to be uploaded to Webin account before run submission.
- Can use multiple tools to upload files using FTP or Aspera.
- Runs can be submitted using a spreadsheet after upload.

Programmatic Data Submission: Run

- Raw read sequencing data object
- Read files can be submitted using XML/JSON file format as shown here.
- Supports several file formats including Fastq, BAM, CRAM, HDF5 and FAST5.
- Read files must be uploaded to the webin account upload area prior to submission.
- Successful submission of the XML/JSON files returns a run accession with the sequence files metadata and an experiment accession with the library metadata.

```
"experiment":[
  {
    "alias":"exp_antis_religiosa",
    "centerName":"EBI",
    "title":"The IKITE project:evolution of insects",
    "study":{
      "accession":"SRP017801"
    },
    "samples":[
      {
        "accession":"SRS462875"
      }
    ],
    "designDescription":"","
    "libraryDescriptor":{
      "libraryName":"unspecified",
      "libraryStrategy":"RNA-Seq",
      "librarySource":"TRANSCRIPTOMIC",
      "librarySelection":"cDNA",
      "libraryLayout":"paired"
    },
    "instrumentPlatform":"ILLUMINA",
    "instrumentModel":"Illumina HSeq 2000",
    "attributes":{
      {
        "tag":"library preparation date",
        "value":"2010-08"
      }
    }
  }
]
```

```
<EXPERIMENT SET>
  <EXPERIMENT alias="exp_mantis_religiosa">
    <TITLE>The IKITE project: evolution of insects</TITLE>
    <STUDY_REF accession="SRP017801"/>
    <DESIGN>
      <DESIGN_DESCRIPTION/>
      <SAMPLE_DESCRIPTOR accession="SRS462875"/>
      <LIBRARY_DESCRIPTOR>
        <LIBRARY_NAME/>
        <LIBRARY_STRATEGY>RNA-Seq</LIBRARY_STRATEGY>
        <LIBRARY_SOURCE>TRANSCRIPTOMIC</LIBRARY_SOURCE>
        <LIBRARY_SELECTION>cDNA</LIBRARY_SELECTION>
        <LIBRARY_LAYOUT>
          <PAIRED NOMINAL_LENGTH="250" NOMINAL_SDEV="30"/>
        </LIBRARY_LAYOUT>
        <LIBRARY_CONSTRUCTION_PROTOCOL>Messenger RNA (mRNA) was i
      </LIBRARY_DESCRIPTOR>
    </DESIGN>
    <PLATFORM>
      <ILLUMINA>
        <INSTRUMENT_MODEL>Illumina HiSeq 2000</INSTRUMENT_MODEL>
      </ILLUMINA>
    </PLATFORM>
    <EXPERIMENT_ATTRIBUTES>
      <EXPERIMENT_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>library preparation date</TAG>
        <VALUE>2010-08</VALUE>
      </EXPERIMENT_ATTRIBUTE>
    </EXPERIMENT_ATTRIBUTES>
  </EXPERIMENT>
</EXPERIMENT_SET>
```

```
<RUN SET>
  <RUN alias="run_mantis_religiosa" center_name="">
    <EXPERIMENT_REF refname="exp_mantis_religiosa"/>
    <DATA_BLOCK>
      <FILES>
        <FILE filename="mantis_religiosa_R1.fastq.gz" filetype="fastq"
          checksum_method="MD5" checksum="9b8932f85caa54e687eba62fca3edce2"/>
        <FILE filename="mantis_religiosa_R2.fastq.gz" filetype="fastq"
          checksum_method="MD5" checksum="183d6a24e0c3704e993bebe75bbbd989"/>
      </FILES>
    </DATA_BLOCK>
  </RUN>
</RUN_SET>
```

Programmatic Data Submission: APIs

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/drop-box/>

- XML file format submissions
- Synchronous endpoint
- Submit one data object in one file

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin-v2/>

- XML and JSON file format submissions
- Synchronous and asynchronous endpoints
- Submit multiple data objects in one file

Programmatic Data Submission

Summary

<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/>

- The ENA provides **scientific record** of sequencing data.
- Established in the early 1980s, extended for **new technologies and applications**.
- Comprehensive record of world's **nucleotide sequencing information** covering raw read data, sequence assembly information and functional annotation.
- Presents large amounts of a diverse range of data in a consistent manner, making use of **Data and Metadata Models**.
- Metadata model requires minimal mandatory metadata in line with **FAIR data principles**.
- Rich submission, discovery and retrieval **software, tools and services**.
- **Support** through Helpdesk and training.
- **Data submission** routes: Interactive, programmatic and Webin-CLI.
- Programmatic Submission using XML and/or JSON **file formats**.
- **Data coordination** including project-specific data hubs and portals.

Handy links

- ENA Browser: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>
- ENA Submission/Retrieval Guide: <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/general-guide.html>
- ENA Helpdesk: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/support>
- Advanced Search: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/advanced-search>
- Webin Portal: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>
- Webin TEST Portal: <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

Thank you

Any Questions?

Programmatic Data Submission Practical

During this exercise, you will implement some of the skills you have just learnt and submit some raw read sequencing data to the ENA.

1. Register a Study Programmatically in JSON file format
2. Register your Sample Programmatically in XML file format
3. Upload Raw Read data files with FTP using FileZilla
4. Submit Read files Programmatically in XML file format

Thank you
Any Questions?

